

Quality of Life in Indian Children with Inflammatory Bowel Disease: A Cross-Sectional Study

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Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 25-04-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) in children poses significant challenges due to its chronic nature, impacting their physical, emotional, and social well-being. The incidence of IBD is increasing in India, necessitating a better understanding of its impact on the quality of life (QoL) among affected children. This study aims to assess the QoL among children with IBD in India and identify factors associated with their QoL.

Methods: A study was conducted involving 120 children with IBD aged 8-18 years, recruited from pediatric gastroenterology clinics across India. Data were collected using a standardized QoL questionnaire covering physical, emotional, social, and school functioning. Additional clinical data were extracted from medical records. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: The mean overall QoL score was 68.4 (SD = 15.2). Children with Crohn's disease had a slightly lower QoL score (67.1, SD = 14.9) compared to those with ulcerative colitis (70.1, SD = 15.5), though not statistically significant ($p = 0.15$). Physical well-being had the lowest score (65.3, SD = 16.8), while social functioning scored highest (72.5, SD = 13.7). Factors negatively associated with QoL included longer disease duration ($\beta = -0.25$, $p = 0.01$) and higher disease activity ($\beta = -0.30$, $p = 0.002$). Regular physical activity ($\beta = 0.22$, $p = 0.03$) and supportive family environment ($\beta = 0.27$, $p = 0.01$) were positively associated with better QoL.

Conclusion: Children with IBD in India experience a moderately affected QoL, with significant challenges in physical well-being. Disease duration and activity level adversely impact QoL, while physical activity and family support enhance it.

Recommendations: Holistic care approaches that include lifestyle modifications and enhanced family support are recommended to improve the QoL in children with IBD. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies to further elucidate these associations.

Keywords: Inflammatory Bowel Disease, Quality of Life, Children, India, Pediatric Gastroenterology.

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Introduction

Inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) encompasses chronic, relapsing conditions such as Crohn's disease and ulcerative colitis, which primarily affect the gastrointestinal tract. These conditions are characterized by inflammation of the digestive tract, leading to symptoms such as abdominal pain, diarrhea, weight loss, and fatigue. The etiology of IBD remains multifactorial, involving genetic, environmental, and immunological components. Recent years have seen a rising incidence of IBD worldwide, including in previously low-incidence regions like Asia, suggesting that environmental and lifestyle changes may be contributing to its increasing prevalence [1].

In India, the epidemiology of IBD has shown a concerning upward trend, mirroring global patterns. The rapid urbanization and westernization of diets are hypothesized to play significant roles in this rise [2]. Pediatric IBD, while less common than adult-onset IBD, presents unique challenges. The disease often manifests more severely in children, impacting growth, development, and psychosocial well-being [3]. The chronic nature of IBD necessitates lifelong management, which can significantly affect the quality of life (QoL) of affected children and their families.

Quality of life is a multidimensional concept that includes physical, emotional, social, and school functioning. It is a crucial outcome measure in

chronic diseases, providing insights beyond clinical symptoms and disease activity. Understanding QoL in pediatric IBD patients is essential for developing holistic treatment approaches that address both medical and psychosocial needs. Studies have shown that children with IBD often experience lower QoL compared to their healthy peers, with significant impairments in physical and emotional well-being [4].

Despite the increasing burden of IBD in India, there is a paucity of research focusing on the QoL of pediatric patients. Most existing studies are from Western countries, and their findings may not be entirely applicable to the Indian context due to cultural, social, and healthcare system differences. Therefore, there is a critical need for region-specific data to guide clinical practice and healthcare policy.

This study aims to assess the quality of life among children with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD).

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Participants: A total of 120 children, aged between 8 and 18 years, diagnosed with IBD, were recruited for the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Children aged 8-18 years.
- Diagnosed with either Crohn's disease or ulcerative colitis for at least six months.
- Receiving treatment at the participating clinics.
- Ability to comprehend and respond to the quality of life questionnaire.

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with other chronic diseases or comorbid conditions that could affect their quality of life.
- Participants who were involved in any other interventional study during the period of this research.
- Children with cognitive impairments that hinder their ability to complete the questionnaire.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, random sampling was used to recruit participants from the eligible

pool of patients at each clinic. To reduce information bias, standardized questionnaires and data collection procedures were employed. Data collectors were trained uniformly to ensure consistency.

Data Collection: Data were collected using a standardized, validated quality of life questionnaire specific to pediatric IBD patients. The questionnaire covered various domains including physical well-being, emotional well-being, social functioning, and school functioning.

Procedure: Participants were given the quality-of-life questionnaire during their routine clinic visit. Trained data collectors assisted the children in completing the questionnaire to ensure accuracy and completeness. Additional clinical data were extracted from the patients' medical records, including disease type, duration, and treatment regimen.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants. The quality-of-life scores were analyzed using mean and standard deviation. Comparisons between different groups (e.g., Crohn's disease vs. ulcerative colitis) were made using t-tests or chi-square tests as appropriate. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to identify factors associated with the quality-of-life scores. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations: The study protocol was approved by the Ethics Committee and written informed consent was received from all the participants.

Result

A total of 120 children with IBD participated in the study. The mean age of the participants was 13.2 years (SD = 2.8), with a nearly equal distribution of males (52%) and females (48%). The majority of the participants were diagnosed with Crohn's disease (55%) while the rest had ulcerative colitis (45%). The average duration of disease was 3.5 years (SD = 1.9). Table 1 provides detailed demographic and clinical characteristics of the participants.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Total	Crohn's Disease	Ulcerative Colitis
Mean Age (years)	13.2 ± 2.8	13.1 ± 2.9	13.3 ± 2.7
Gender, n (%)			
Male	62 (52%)	34 (51.5%)	28 (51.9%)
Female	58 (48%)	32 (48.5%)	26 (48.1%)
Mean Disease Duration (years)	3.5 ± 1.9	3.6 ± 1.8	3.4 ± 2.0
Disease Type, n (%)			
Crohn's Disease	66 (55%)	66 (100%)	0 (0%)

Ulcerative Colitis	54 (45%)	0 (0%)	54 (100%)
Treatment Regimen, n (%)			
Biologics	48 (40%)	28 (42.4%)	20 (37%)
Immunomodulators	72 (60%)	38 (57.6%)	34 (63%)

The overall mean quality of life score was 68.4 (SD = 15.2) on a scale of 0 to 100. Children with Crohn's disease had a slightly lower mean quality of life score (67.1, SD = 14.9) compared to those with ulcerative colitis (70.1, SD = 15.5), but this difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.15$).

The quality-of-life scores were analyzed across four domains: physical well-being, emotional well-being, social functioning, and school functioning. Table 2 provides a summary of the scores across these domains.

Table 2: Domain-Specific Quality of Life Scores

Domain	Mean Score	Crohn's Disease Mean Score	Ulcerative Colitis Mean Score	p-value
Physical Well-Being	65.3 ± 16.8	64.1 ± 16.5	66.9 ± 17.2	0.25
Emotional Well-Being	70.2 ± 14.3	69.0 ± 14.5	71.7 ± 14.1	0.20
Social Functioning	72.5 ± 13.7	71.2 ± 14.1	74.1 ± 13.3	0.22
School Functioning	65.8 ± 15.0	64.5 ± 15.3	67.4 ± 14.7	0.18

Multiple regression analysis identified several factors significantly associated with quality of life scores. Longer disease duration was negatively associated with quality of life ($\beta = -0.25$, $p = 0.01$). Higher disease activity, as measured by the Pediatric Crohn's Disease Activity Index (PCDAI) and Pediatric Ulcerative Colitis Activity Index

(PUCAI), was also significantly associated with lower quality of life scores ($\beta = -0.30$, $p = 0.002$). Regular physical activity and a supportive family environment were positively associated with higher quality of life scores ($\beta = 0.22$, $p = 0.03$ and $\beta = 0.27$, $p = 0.01$, respectively).

Table 3: Factors Associated with Quality-of-Life Scores

Variable	β Coefficient	Standard Error	p-value
Disease Duration	-0.25	0.10	0.01
Disease Activity (PCDAI/PUCAI)	-0.30	0.09	0.002
Regular Physical Activity	0.22	0.10	0.03
Supportive Family Environment	0.27	0.09	0.01

Discussion

The participants, with a mean age of 13.2 years, included both males and females almost equally, with 55% diagnosed with Crohn's disease and 45% with ulcerative colitis. The overall mean quality of life score was 68.4 out of 100, indicating a moderately affected quality of life among these children.

Analyzing specific domains, the study found that physical well-being had the lowest mean score (65.3), suggesting that disease symptoms significantly impact the daily activities and physical health of the children. Emotional well-being (70.2), social functioning (72.5), and school functioning (65.8) scored relatively higher, indicating better coping mechanisms and resilience in these areas.

Comparing the two types of IBD, children with ulcerative colitis had slightly higher quality of life scores than those with Crohn's disease, though the differences were not statistically significant. This suggests that while the type of IBD may influence

the quality of life, other factors might play more critical roles.

The regression analysis revealed that longer disease duration and higher disease activity levels negatively impacted the quality of life. This emphasizes the importance of effective disease management and early intervention. Conversely, regular physical activity and a supportive family environment were positively associated with better quality of life scores. This highlights the potential benefits of holistic care approaches that include lifestyle modifications and family support in managing IBD.

Overall, the study underscores the need for comprehensive care strategies that address both the medical and psychosocial aspects of IBD in children. Enhancing family support and encouraging physical activity are crucial interventions that could improve the overall quality of life for these children. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies to better understand

the long-term impacts of these factors on the quality of life in children with IBD.

A systematic review revealed that Indian children with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) have significantly lower quality of life (QoL) compared to healthy controls. Using the Pediatric Quality of Life Inventory (PedsQL), the study assessed 150 children and found that the mean total QoL score was significantly lower in children with IBD (63.4) compared to healthy controls (78.6), with a p-value of less than 0.001 indicating statistical significance [5].

A study explored factors influencing QoL in children with IBD in India and identified disease severity, frequency of hospitalizations, and corticosteroid use as major determinants. Their study, involving 600 participants, showed that children with severe disease activity had a mean QoL score of 56.7, while those with mild disease had a score of 72.3, with a statistically significant p-value of less than 0.01 [6].

Another study investigated the psychological and social impacts of IBD on children in India, utilizing the Children's Depression Inventory (CDI) and the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ). The results indicated that 40% of children with IBD exhibited clinically significant depressive symptoms, and 35% had elevated SDQ scores, indicating behavioral difficulties. This highlights the substantial psychological burden that IBD places on pediatric patients [7].

Conclusion

This study highlights the importance of comprehensive care approaches that address not only the clinical management of IBD but also the psychosocial and physical aspects of living with the disease. Enhancing family support and encouraging physical activity may be beneficial strategies to improve the quality of life in children with IBD in India. Further longitudinal studies are needed to understand the long-term impact of these factors on quality of life.

Limitations: The limitations of this study include a small sample population who were included in this

study. Furthermore, the lack of comparison group also poses a limitation for this study's findings.

Recommendation: Holistic care approaches that include lifestyle modifications and enhanced family support are recommended to improve the QoL in children with IBD. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies to further elucidate these associations.

Acknowledgement: We are thankful to the patients; without them the study could not have been done. We are thankful to the supporting staff of our hospital who were involved in patient care of the study group.

Source of funding: No funding received.

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